

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by morpholinium chlorochromate

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Abstract : Oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes by morpholinium chlorochromate (MCC) in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding carboxylic acids. The reaction is first order each in MCC and the aldehyde. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde, MeCDO, exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}} = 5.95$ at 298 K). The oxidation of acetaldehyde has been studied in 19 different organic solvents. The solvent effect has been analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The rate constants correlate well with Taft's σ^* values and reaction constants are negative. A mechanism involving transfer of hydride ion has been suggested.

Keywords : Kinetics, morpholinium chlorochromate, aldehydes, oxidation, mechanism.

Introduction

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹. In continuation of our earlier work², we report here the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes by MCC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent.

Results and discussion

The experimental data obtained for all the aldehydes are similar and are reported in the Table 1. The oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by MCC leads to the formation of corresponding carboxylic acids. The overall reaction may be written as :

MCC undergoes two-electron change as reported for other substituted chromates². The rate law is also similar to other substituted chromates as reported earlier. A plot of absorbance against time depicted a typical kinetic (Fig. 1). The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the plots of $\log [\text{oxidant}]$ against time for at least two half lives. The rate constants were also checked by substituting values in first order rate equation given

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of acetaldehyde by MCC at 298 K

$10^3 [\text{MCC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{MeCHO}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$[\text{PTS}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	4.86
1.00	0.20	0.00	9.63
1.00	0.40	0.00	19.1
1.00	0.60	0.00	28.8
1.00	0.80	0.00	38.7
1.00	1.00	0.00	48.2
2.00	0.40	0.00	20.7
4.00	0.40	0.00	19.8
6.00	0.40	0.00	19.0
8.00	0.40	0.00	21.7
1.00	0.10	0.10	5.67
1.00	0.10	0.20	6.75
1.00	0.10	0.40	8.34
1.00	0.10	0.60	9.75
1.00	0.10	0.80	12.0
1.00	0.10	1.00	13.9
1.00	0.20	0.00	9.72 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

below,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = (2.303/t) \log a/(a-x) \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Oxidation of acetaldehyde by MCC, a typical kinetic run.

The oxidation of acetaldehyde by MCC, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1). Thus a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely.

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the aldehydic C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde (MeCDO) was studied. The oxidation of deuteriated acetaldehyde exhibited a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

Fig. 2. Effect of temperature on rate, Arrhenius plot.

$4.76 \pm 0.19 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $8.97 \pm 0.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively ($r^2 = 0.9949$).

The oxidation of acetaldehyde was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of MCC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics was similar in all the solvents. The values k_2 are recorded in Table 4. The

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by MCC

Subst.	$10^4 k_2 \text{ (dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}\text{)}$				ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	1.36	3.11	7.11	16.2	60.3 ± 0.7	-110 ± 2	92.9 ± 0.6
Me	23.4	48.2	99.5	204	52.4 ± 0.7	-114 ± 3	86.2 ± 0.6
Et	41.8	84.4	171	342	50.9 ± 0.8	-114 ± 3	84.8 ± 0.8
Pr	45.6	91.8	185	370	50.6 ± 0.6	-115 ± 2	84.6 ± 0.5
Pr ⁱ	70.5	139	277	546	49.5 ± 0.7	-115 ± 3	83.6 ± 0.7
ClCH ₂	0.053	0.14	0.35	0.89	68.9 ± 0.7	-107 ± 3	99.9 ± 0.7
MeCDO	3.52	8.25	18.3	41.7	56.4 ± 0.9	-115 ± 2	90.6 ± 0.6
k_H/k_D	6.24	5.95	5.69	5.31			

The rates of oxidation of six aliphatic aldehydes were determined at four different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2). The $\log k_2$ at different temperatures is linearly related to the inverse of the absolute temperature in all the cases (Fig. 2). The Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for this reaction.

The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 3). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. Values of a and b , for acetaldehyde, are

activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the nine aliphatic alcohols are linearly related ($r = 0.9938$). The value of isokinetic temperature³ evaluated from this plot is $2327 \pm 95 \text{ K}$. The correlation was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion⁴. An Exner's plot (Fig. 3) between $\log k_2$ at 288 K and at 318 K was linear ($r = 0.9994$). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's plot is $2308 \pm 71 \text{ K}$. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of acetaldehyde by MCC at 308 K

Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	$10^4 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	27.5	Acetic acid	4.27
1,2-Dichloromethane	31.6	Cyclohexane	1.38
Dichloromethane	34.7	Toluene	9.12
DMSO	99.5	Acetophenone	47.9
Acetone	28.8	THF	15.5
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	56.2	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	11.2
Butanone	21.8	1,4-Dioxane	18.2
Nitrobenzene	41.7	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	8.32
Benzene	12.0	Carbon disulfide	5.25
Ethyl acetate	13.5		

Table 4. Temperature dependence of the reaction constant

Temp. (K)	288	298	308	318
ρ^*	-2.52 ± 0.01	-2.42 ± 0.03	-2.34 ± 0.01	-2.25 ± 0.01
r^2	0.9999	0.9998	0.9999	0.9998
σ	0.001	0.003	0.007	0.006

Fig. 3. Isokinetic relationship in the oxidation of aldehydes with MCC.

are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in rate are governed by the changes in both the enthalpy and

entropy of the activation. The oxidation reaction proceeds through two pathways one is acid-independent and the other one is acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of MCC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile (2). Both MCC and MCCH^+ are reactive species with the protonated form being more reactive,

The oxidation of acetaldehyde was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvents was limited due to the solubility of QBC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values k_2 at 308 K are recorded in Table 3. The rate constants, k_2 , in eighteen solvents (CS_2 was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) were correlated in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (3) of Kamlet *et al.*⁵,

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + \rho\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (4)$$

In this equation, π^* represents the solvent polarity, β the hydrogen bond acceptor basicities and α is the hydrogen bond donor acidity. A_0 is the intercept term. It may be mentioned here that out of the 18 solvents, 12 have a value of zero for α . The results of correlation analyses in terms of (4), a biparametric equation involving π^* and β , and separately with π^* and β are given below as eqs. (5)–(8),

$$\log k_2 = -4.22 + 1.54 (\pm 0.20) \pi^* + 0.19 (\pm 0.16) \beta + 0.26 (\pm 0.15) \alpha \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8590; \sigma = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.15 + 1.64 (\pm 0.20) \pi^* + 0.10 (\pm 0.16) \beta \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8309; \sigma = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.44$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.18 + 1.67 (\pm 0.19) \pi^* \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8263; \sigma = 0.19; n = 18; \psi = 0.43$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.89 + 0.40 (\pm 0.36) \beta \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0702; \sigma = 0.44; n = 18; \psi = 0.99$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter⁶. Kamlet's triparametric equation explains *ca.* 86% of the effect of solvent on the oxidation. However, by Exner's criterion the correlation is not even satisfactory [*cf.* (5)]. The major contribution is of solvent polarity. It alone accounted for *ca.* 83% of the data. Both β and α play relatively minor roles. The data

on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation⁷ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also as eq. (9),

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (9)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (8), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.43 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.71 (\pm 0.02) B - 4.01 \quad (10)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9966; \sigma = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.06$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.19 (\pm 0.56) A - 2.82 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0063; \sigma = 0.45; n = 19; \psi = 1.02$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.67 (\pm 0.08) B - 4.15 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9632; \sigma = 0.09; n = 19; \psi = 0.20$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.28 \pm 0.16 (A+B) - 4.05 \quad (13)$$

$$r^2 = 0.7813; \sigma = 0.21; n = 19; \psi = 0.48$$

The rates of oxidation of acetaldehyde in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation [cf. (9)] with the cation-solvating power playing the major role (96%). The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for ca. 78% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for ca. 78% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r_2 = 0.5262$; $\sigma = 0.31$; $\psi = 0.71$).

Mechanism : In aqueous solutions most aliphatic aldehydes exist predominantly in the hydrated form and in many oxidations, in aqueous solutions, it has been postulated that the hydrate is the reactive species⁸. However, owing to the non-aqueous nature of the solvent in the present reaction, only the free carbonyl form can be the reactive species. The rates of the oxidation of six aldehydes show an excellent correlation with Taft's σ^* substituent constants⁹, the reaction constant being negative (Table 4). The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. There is no kinetic evidence for the formation of an intermediate in the present reaction, however, its formation in small amounts can not be ruled out. The presence of a substantial primary kinetic

isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.95$ at 298 K) indicates that the aldehydic C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. The large negative value of the polar reaction constant together with the substantial deuterium isotope effect indicates that the transition state approaches a carbocation in character. Hence, transfer of a hydride ion from the aldehyde to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride ion transfer mechanism is also supported by major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents,

High values of activation indicate that in the rate determining step bond breaking is more important in transition state. Large negative entropy of activation supports a transition state formed from two independent molecules.

Experimental

Materials : MCC was prepared by the reported method¹⁰. Solutions of formaldehyde were prepared by heating paraformaldehyde and passing its vapours in DMSO. The amount of HCHO in DMSO was determined by chromotropic acid method¹¹. Other aldehydes were commercial products and were used as such. *p*-Toluenesulphonic acid (PTS) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Deuteriated acetaldehyde (MeCDO) was obtained from Sigma Chemicals. Solvents were purified by their usual methods.

Product analysis : In a typical experiment, acetaldehyde (4.4 g, 0.1 mol) and MCC (3.27 g, 0.01 mol) were dissolved in DMSO (100 ml) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for ca. ≈ 24 h to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then made alkaline with NaOH, filtered and the amount of filtrate was reduced to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was acidified with perchloric acid and extracted with diethyl ether (5%, 50 ml). The ether extract was dried (MgSO_4) and treated with 10 ml of thionyl chloride. The solvent was allowed to evaporate. Dry methanol (7 ml) was added and the HCl formed was removed in a current of dry air. The residue was dissolved in diethyl ether (200 ml) and the ester content was determined colorimetrically as Fe^{III}

hydroxymate by the procedure of Hall and Schaefer¹². The determinations indicated a 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The oxidation state of chromium in a completely reduced reaction mixture, determined by iodometric titrations was 3.90 ± 0.10 .

Kinetic measurements: Pseudo-first order conditions were attained by keeping an excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the [aldehyde] over [MCC] in DMSO solvent unless mentioned otherwise. All reactions were carried out in flasks blackened from the outside to prevent any photochemical reactions at constant temperature (± 0.1 K) and were followed up to 80% of the extent of reaction, by monitoring the decrease in [MCC] at 370 nm. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was computed from the linear least-squares plot of \log [MCC] versus time. Duplicate runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was calculated from the relation : $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{aldehyde}]$.

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